

Thematic Progression: A Comparative Analysis of Social Science Research Articles Written by Pakistani and British Research Scholars

Correspondence:	Sadia Munir <sadiapak72@yahoo.com>	Research Scholar & Visiting Lecturer, Government College University, Faisalabad, Punjab, Pakistan.
	Shagufta Afzal <shaguftaafzal13@gmail.com>	Research Scholar & Visiting Lecturer, The Islamia University, Bahawalpur, Punjab, Pakistan.
	Hafsa Tazeen <hafsatazeen50@gmail.com>	Research Scholar & Visiting Lecturer, Education University, Johrabad Campus, Punjab, Pakistan.

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Abstract

Cohesion plays a crucial role in shaping the texture of a text through appropriate thematic choices. Recognizing the issue of cohesion, the researcher conducted a present study to address this problem. The study focused on analyzing social science research articles authored by Pakistani and British research scholars, employing thematic terminologies and emphasizing the textual metafunction. The objectives were twofold: first, to explore and compare the thematic meanings expressed in Pakistani and British social science research articles, and second, to elucidate the functional interpretation of the identified themes. The researcher conducted a qualitative analysis of the data in three steps: (1) dividing the text into clauses, (2) identifying theme components, and (3) tagging the components according to their types and sub-types of themes. The results revealed that the prominent sub-types of themes were the unmarked topical theme (UMT), finite, continuatives, and conjunctions in the topical, interpersonal, and textual themes, respectively. The topical themes served as noun groups, while the textual themes connected new information with prior information. The qualitative analysis focused on studying the patterns of cohesion, leading the researcher to thematic progression and explaining the relationship between theme and rheme within a text. This relationship and its interpretation demonstrated that cohesion relies on thematic choices. Furthermore, the study found that British research articles exhibited greater cohesion compared to Pakistani research articles.

Keywords: cohesion, systemic functional linguistics, Pakistani research writing, (un)marked topical themes

1. Introduction

The current study is a comparative analysis that examines the thematic structures of social science research articles authored by Pakistani and British research scholars. The term "Theme" is a technical concept in Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL), specifically related to the textual metafunction. This research sheds light on the utilization of themes in social science research articles from Pakistan and Britain. According to Nunan (1993), the theme is defined as the initial position of a sentence or clause that serves as a prominent grammatical element and establishes a connection with the subsequent clause.

1.1 Research Background

From the perspective of SFL, every language constitutes a semiotic act of meaning. Language has evolved to serve a purpose in human lives and reflects a positive impact on various tasks. Understanding language requires an examination of the implications generated within a social context.

SFL views language through two semantic aspects:

- Each speaker possesses a semiotic framework through which they convey their intended meaning. However, the presence of multiple semiotic options can cause confusion and hinder effective communication.
- When discussing a particular perspective within the socially constructed framework, adhering to the semiotic principles leads to accurate outcomes.

1.2 Statement of Problem

In the context of academic writing, the researcher identified the presence of jumbled information, which falls within the scope of the research's focal point (textual metafunction). This problematic area motivated the researcher to conduct a thematic analysis of academic writing. To narrow down the scope, the researcher specifically focused on social science research articles authored by Pakistani and British research scholars.

1.3 Objectives of this Study

The study had two main objectives:

- To explore and articulate the thematic meanings present in written texts of social science research articles from both Pakistani and British contexts.
- To provide a functional interpretation of the themes identified in the articles.

1.4 Research Questions of this Study

The following research questions considered to find out the solution of the present study.

1. How are the thematic meanings realized in the written text of Pakistani and British research articles?
2. What is the functional interpretation of the theme found in Pakistani and British research articles?

1.5 De-limitations of the Research

To enhance the credibility of the study, the researcher made specific delimitations, as outlined below:

- The scope of this research was limited to the analysis of written texts.
- The written texts were sourced from research articles published in Pakistan and Britain.
- The analysis focused on the textual metafunction, employing thematic terminology as the analytical tool.
- The research articles were confined to the field of social science.
- The selected research articles were published between 2019 and 2020.

2. Literature Review

According to Halliday (1994, p. 15), a language is a system or network which have an opinion for the formation of meaning. It does not provide directions for sentence structures. At the lexico-grammatical level, Halliday (1994) introduces three metafunctions:

“Ideational”	-	generating a paradigm of experience
“Interpersonal”	-	generating social relationships
“Textual”	-	generating a connection to the context

The two grammatical devices (Theme and Rheme) are major features of the textual metafunction. Halliday defined, “theme is a first position holder in a clause which considers cohesion of a clause” (Halliday, 1994, p. 37). In any language, a theme is more important for identification, for what the message is about. In English, a theme is realized by the first position element, and this first placement grants distinctive eminence to the theme into a clause.

2.1 Theoretical Framework

This section elaborates various points. It gives a very strong base to the textual metafunction.

2.1.1 Metafunctions of Language

2.1.1.1 Semantic Feature

The system of semantic is defined as “formation of a text”, in which the four different types meaning are expressed through word choices; experiential, logical, interpersonal and textual. These different types of word choices generate a new meaning of a clause. The differences of these terms are following:

- a. In a clause structure, the theme works as a message; a popular category, that has an explicit meaning as a message. A starting point of a message, which analyzes the essence of the statement or information in a clause.
- b. The theme acts as an exchange in a clause structure, which generates significant message by the result of exchanging of words among narrator and listener.
- c. In a clause structure, the third one is as representation. A representation clause places the actor as an active participant in each interaction process.

2.1.1.2 System of Three Semantic Features

2.1.1.2.1 The Textual Metafunction-Clause as Message

The interpretation of language is revealed through the textual metafunction, which functions as a message (Halliday, 1994, p. 37). According to Davidse (1987), both intrinsic and extrinsic language serve as metafunctions and represent distinct elements of grammar or principles of semantic organization. However, the ideational and interpersonal functions ultimately refer to social reality. Davidse suggests that Halliday's theory emphasizes metafunction as it illustrates the systematic association between language organization and the field, tenor, and mode variables (1987, p. 57). The initial position of a clause plays a crucial role in establishing the clause context. Textual coherence is achieved by ensuring relevance to the context, which is significant in both spoken and written texts. The clause's function is to construct a message, with the key system being the theme (Halliday, 1994, p. 36).

In their PhD thesis, Fahimnia (2009) evaluated Halliday's thematic function strategy by examining Persian books for primary school learners. Fahimnia's findings demonstrated the adaptability of Halliday's systemic grammar categories. Similarly, Kazemi (2012) explored the themes and rhemes in nineteen articles and six books on science texts in Persian and English. In addition to examining labeled topics in these languages, Kazemi conducted a comparative and contrastive analysis of the framework, revealing its various aspects.

The utilization of the textual metafunction enhances the significance of the clause as a message, facilitating effective communication. The objective is to organize the presented texts into a cohesive theme. It involves organizing information within individual statements in written form. Furthermore, the thematic division into different categories plays a vital role in cohesion. By implementing the theme-rheme system and organizing information effectively, the unity of a text can be maintained.

2.1.1.2.2 Thematic Relations and their Sub-Systems

The concept of theme/rheme consists of two distinct components:

- Pure definitions of meaning: Different scholars offer definitions for theme and rheme based on their theoretical perspectives.
- Applied definitions: Scholars also provide practical versions of these definitions, which contribute to the context of language learning.

Kularb (2001) conducted research on the characteristics of theme and rheme in student discourse. The study involved analyzing written texts from nine students, conducting interviews with the students, and observing classroom teachers. The findings revealed that learners encounter challenges with both theme and rheme. These challenges include issues with conjunctions, missing sentence topics, redundancy, and interference from their native language.

2.1.1.2.3 Types of Theme

The dimensional metafunction encompasses three types of themes within a clause: topical, interpersonal, and textual. Each type is explained below:

2.1.1.2.3.1 The Experiential/Topical theme

The experiential stage of the theme is commonly referred to as the topical theme. It denotes the initial placement within a statement. The topical theme can be classified into two types: unmarked topical theme (UMT) and marked topical theme (MT).

The UMT theme functions as a noun group, noun complex group, or embedded clause. Conversely, the MT theme functions as an adjunct or complement, further classified into adverbial group and prepositional group.

2.1.1.2.3.2 The Interpersonal Theme

The interpersonal theme pertains to the expression of the writer's or speaker's judgment on meaning. It encompasses modal adjuncts, vocatives, finite or WH-elements. The interpersonal theme also plays a role in mood clauses, where major clauses include social themes while minor clauses do not.

Indicative, imperative, declarative, and questioning clauses, along with yes/no integrative or WH-clauses, are considered significant. Modal (Adjunct) is typically an adverb that conveys the speaker's comments, evaluations, or attitudes towards the message. Vocatives, on the other hand, are used to address someone, usually by their personal name. They can appear anywhere in the sentence, and if they precede the topical theme, they become thematic.

WH-Interrogative themes indicate that the addressee requires an answer. Their function is to specify the entity that the questioner seeks to be provided. The WH-element establishes a connection between different topical themes, representing a participant or circumstance. In this way, the WH-element can simultaneously serve as a topical theme.

2.1.1.2.3.3 The Textual Theme

Continuous, conjunctive, and conjunctive adjunct are the forms of the textual theme, when it is having the first placement in a clause. The discourse signalers like yes, no, well, oh are the continuatives, which shows that a new move is starting, and they do not choose either positive or negative, i.e. they reflect the current polarity. Structural interconnections combine two segments to show a coordinating relationship or mark one clause as dependent on another. Relative elements can be served as both textual and topical themes since they relate two different relative clauses. The conjunctive adjunct brings a cohesive connection back to the previous speech. Wherever it happens, the topical themes precede it.

2.1.1.2.3.4 Thematic Equatives

There is not any entity, which can be said as thematic equative and to produce a thematic system. It is a situation, in which two equal but different clauses lie together to produce a sentence in the structure of theme and rheme. This situation is called thematic equatives. An example of this would be:

What he gave my aunt was this kettle.

2.1.1.2.3.5 Predicated Theme

A key feature of thematic equative is that they combine more than one message element into a single sentence component, acting as a theme. Another thematic structure allows the speaker to highlight a single element and give it an emphatic thematic status.

2.1.1.2.3.6 Thematic Progression

David Butt elaborated the thematic progression in his book "Using Functional Grammar" as, the themes are function as signpost in a text that tells what kind of new information is coming in the rheme to a reader or addressee. He exemplified different styles of thematic progression to clear up the role of cohesion. One of the patterns is following, which had used in this study for data analysis.

2.1.2 Model

This study concerned the Systemic Functional Grammar and textual metafunction further. This field has different models and revised models as well. This study needed an adopted or produced scheme for analysis. The researcher went through various models and decided to work with two models. These models have been taken from two books. The one is entitled “Introducing Functional Grammar”, the third edition revised by Geoff Thompson in 2014. The other is entitled “An Introduction to Functional Grammar” by M.A.K. Halliday and Christian Matthiessen in (2004) revised by Christian Matthiessen in (2014).

2.1.3 New Schemata

2.2 Previous Studies

The researcher selected previous literature that consisted of relevant studies to the present research. These studies have demonstrated the significance of the term theme-rheme in text organization and interpretation.

In 2013, Asri Nur Rahman conducted a study that revealed the challenges faced by most pupils in terms of writing coherence. The study found that pupils tend to focus more on individual words and sentences rather than the overall discourse. The researcher examined nine exposition texts with varying levels of accomplishment, selected based on the thematic progression framework. The study identified three patterns used by students to organize their thoughts in a text: various theme, zigzag, and reiteration patterns. Thematic analysis was employed by the researcher to understand the purpose of the exposition texts and to analyze the cohesive devices used. The researcher aimed to determine if students' thoughts align with the different elements of argumentative language.

Isabel Alonso (2016) conducted a study titled "Theme-rheme Pattern in L2 Writing, University Autonoma de Madrid." The study addressed the issue of ESL writing teachers primarily focusing on errors below the sentence level, such as incorrect verb usage and subject-verb agreement. The research aimed to investigate how the Merhem device could be used to improve the writing of L2 students at the discourse level. The study emphasized the potential utility of this construct in second language teaching. The main objective was to demonstrate that thematic rhemes can be a valuable tool for teachers to evaluate L2 students' writing. A quantitative analysis using a T-test was conducted on compositions written by 25 native Spanish speakers learning English as a second language. The study aimed to assist students in developing ideas about thematic development and selection, providing material for classroom activities and enhancing their writing skills.

The similarity between these two studies lies in the use of theme as a tool for analysis. Both researchers sought to establish coherence and cohesion in their respective subjects, with the present researcher utilizing descriptive drawings as a teaching tool to assess L2 students' writing. However, the previous research focused on finding coherence and cohesiveness to support the teaching and learning process, which differentiates it from the present thesis. The writing of L2 students serves as the material for examination in addition to its completion.

Wei Jing conducted the study "Theme and Thematic Progression in English Writing Teaching" in 2015 at Southwest University China's College of International Studies. The study explored the importance of thematic and thematic progression (T/TP) in constructing messages that seamlessly integrate into the developing speech event. Previous studies had demonstrated the value of observing T/TP in identifying writing challenges among English language learners. The study proposed incorporating T/TP into English writing instruction to enhance students' descriptive and qualitative coherence. English language students were selected as participants, and the research aimed to address the research question of creating and examining teaching resources based on T/TP. The study developed a T/TP teaching package for Chinese EFL students by incorporating ideas from Systemic Functional Grammar and relevant literature.

The researcher in both theses aimed to focus on the use of thematic progression (T/TP), monitor it through systemic functional grammar, and evaluate relevant literature. The main objective was to enhance students' understanding of coherence and T/TP in order to provide them with grammatical resources to improve the coherence of their writing and teach them how information and ideas should flow in a text for better reader comprehension. Additionally, students would be able to apply their knowledge of T/TP patterns in English writing to enhance their writing skills. The students' English writing served as the primary data collection instrument for the study.

Recent contributions in the study of textuality have explored themes, thematic frameworks, and thematic progression in texts written in various languages to understand how academic texts develop conceptually. Coherence, as defined by Halliday and Hassan (1976), refers to the relationship between clauses or sentences within a text and their surrounding context. Each paragraph establishes a background for the interpretation of the next paragraph, ensuring coherence. Halliday (Hasselgard, 2000) categorizes themes into three types: experiential, social, and literary.

Textual resource language, according to Stillar (1998), utilizes the resources of the textual function to structure the flow of information, connect different parts of the text, and link the text with its context. Halliday (1994) defines thematization as the movement of sentence elements to their initial positions, along with any grammatical alterations resulting from this movement.

Several studies have explored theme patterns and thematic progression in different languages. For example, Zhou (2006) compared Chinese and English advertisements and found grammatical differences in thematic patterns between the two languages. Denardi et al. (2007) analyzed academic abstracts and observed a zigzag pattern of thematic structure, which contributed to the coherence and texture of the abstracts. Hu (2008) investigated Chinese and American college students' English writing and discovered differences in the use of simple, numerous, and clausal themes.

Paiva and Freitas (2011) conducted a case study on the textual metafunction of Halliday's SFL as a pedagogical tool for evaluating cohesion and coherence in L2 writing. The results highlighted the importance of analyzing learners' writing at a discourse-level perspective to improve the quality and effectiveness of feedback. Jallilifar and Khedri (2011) focused on thematic progression and development in English academic papers and their Persian translations, identifying distinctions between the two text types. Adebola (2011) explored the theme-rheme model in text messages and emphasized its role in strengthening text comprehension and message conveyance. Ebrahimi and Khedri (2012) examined thematic progressions and structures and their impact on message organization and communication.

Khedri (2012) emphasized the importance of thematic structures in students' writing cohesion and highlighted the need for teachers to teach students how to connect sentences to produce coherent and cohesive texts. Jing (2013) studied theme choices in Chinese English learners' speech and found that topical themes brought them closer to native speakers. Ghaleasadi (2013) analyzed English romantic and criminal short stories and identified the use of textual themes, demonstrating the influence of genre on theme choices.

Wang (2014) focused solely on the metafunction of texts, while also tracking the evolution and integration of SFL with translation studies. Both SFL and Theme/Rheme analysis provide fundamental terminologies. The following section presents a review of previous studies on thematic analysis and translation. This discovery helps bridge the gap between descriptive translation studies and SFL, as SFL systematically connects language choices to the sociocultural context.

In Hasan's study (2015), thematic patterns were identified in the translations of "A Haunted House" by Virginia Woolf, "The Tell-Tale Heart" and "Black Cat" by Edgar Allan Poe. The study aimed to compare the reliance on thematic structures in Arabic and English. It revealed potential issues in the translation of English literary works into Arabic due to markedness, topicalization, and concentration. The analysis identified the use of markedness as a literary device in "The Black Cat," "The Tell-Tale Heart," and "A Haunted House." Furthermore, the Arabic translations manipulated the linguistically marked English literary pieces differently.

Damayanti (2016) examined theme equivalence, theme shifts, and theme analysis in the Indonesian-English translation of thesis abstracts. The data included 10 abstracts from the Postgraduate Program at Semarang State University, along with their English translations. The findings showed that all texts predominantly had a topical theme, with 80.16% (198 out of 247) in the source text (ST) and 79.56% (222 out of 279) in the target text (TT). There were no interpersonal themes in either the ST or TT. Most current topics were followed by circumstances and processes involving participants.

In both studies, the literary theme appeared as a conjunctive adjunct. The majority of themes (70.2%) were considered non-shift or comparable. Theme changes were achieved through three methods: (i) altering the theme grammar (11.7%); (ii) introducing new themes (14.7%); and (iii) eliminating themes (3.4%). It is recommended for translators to have a comprehensive understanding of the grammatical structures in both the source language (SL) and target language (TL), as well as an awareness of theme shift and equivalence concepts and their applications.

Puspa (2016) conducted research on the theme and rheme of the short story "Twelve Dancing Princesses" using a functional grammar approach. The findings revealed two categories of themes: topical and textual themes. Interpersonal motifs were not found in this study. Textual themes included elements such as conjunctive adjunct, conjunctive, structural, continuative, and conjunction. Topical themes comprised subject and topical theme (adverbial as a theme). The study aimed to determine the relationship between theme and text development by identifying and categorizing the text of the short story.

Hence, by understanding the theme-rheme composition of a work, one can observe how the author expresses their original concerns word by clause. The current study focused only on the subject and rheme of the short narrative "Twelve Dancing Princesses." This may result in literary and topical themes. The study successfully identified the components of a theme and attempted to establish a connection between theme and text development.

Stoian and Dejica (2016) undertook the "Theme-Rheme Analysis of English and Romanian Tourism Websites" project. They evaluated the theme, rheme, and interpretation of commercial websites from Great Britain and Romania on a small scale. The study focused on three works and provided a global online list of World Heritage Sites for each text. It began with an analysis and comparison of the texts, viewing their themes and thematic structures from a systems functional perspective, following Halliday's textual analysis paradigm.

Ezeifeke (2016) conducted an "Analysis of thematic prominence in selected Nigerian inaugural political speeches." The study aimed to examine how speaker selections in relation to topics influenced the meanings of two inaugural speeches. It was observed that speakers made deliberate decisions on what to highlight and emphasize as breaking news. The analysis revealed that texts convey more than just the words they contain, as their placement within the grammar of the clause plays a crucial role. Therefore, it is recommended to thoroughly study texts to prevent additional hidden meanings generated by the packaging of the message from influencing official meanings. Understanding this crucial language is essential for Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA).

Stella (2017) investigated theme and rheme structures used in the websites of five-star hotels in Surabaya in her thesis titled "An Analysis of Theme and Rheme Used in the Five-Star Hotel's Web Sites in Surabaya." The study demonstrated that hotels primarily use the primary or fundamental structures of theme and rheme in crafting the messages on their websites, rather than the modified second structure. The theme and rheme structures on the hotels' websites were categorized into two primary categories.

Nurlela, Gustiaingsih, Sofyan, and Rosa (2017), focusing on the textual metafunction from SFL, identified the typical features of Indonesian narrative texts. The features included the frequent use of marked theme clauses, process and circumstance as theme elements, numerous theme clauses, and the prevalence of continual continuous theme. These characteristics were discovered during the translation of the novel "Hikayat Deli" from Malay to Bahasa Indonesia.

Koutchadé (2017) conducted research on "Exploring Textual Metafunction in Selected Nigerian News Reports: Linguistic Description and Interpretation." Through linguistic analysis, the study evaluated the language used in two news reports. The investigation of textual meaning facilitated the identification of discourse mode in the texts, which describes the function of language in communication and relates it to the text's meaning. The two texts employed language to describe experiences, without direct interaction between the writers and readers. The analysis of the news stories revealed meanings related to the statements of the Chibok girls, the Nigerian government's negotiation attempts for their release, the girls' meeting with their parents, and the Nigerian military's fight against terrorism.

Astuti (2018) examined the growth and organization of themes in "Sports Texts in the WASPADA Newspaper: Theme Structure." The sports literature in Waspada utilized theme and rheme to establish thematic frameworks. The sports texts predominantly employed a simple thematic structure and exhibited a variety of themes. Throughout the entire work, the unmarked theme dominated the sports texts in Waspada, beginning each clause to convey intriguing information and engage the reader.

Thematic analysis has been applied in various research projects using different types of data. However, the current study focuses on corpus-based theme analysis of academic literature, specifically social science research articles authored by Pakistani and British research academics in 2019 and 2020. This field of study has not been extensively explored in previous research projects. The study provides valuable insights for students, aspiring researchers, educators, and professionals working in the field of education.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1 Research Design

According to Schumacher and Macmillan, a research design is a set of structures, techniques, and plans of an investigation that leads the research questions to their answers. This qualitative research approached to investigate the questions of the present research. The study was conducted to analyze Pakistani and British research articles' written text. The thematic relations have been applied to the written text.

3.2 Sampling and Data Collection

To achieve the objectives of the current study, social science research articles written by Pakistani and British research scholars were collected in pdf form using different national and international journals.

Convenience sampling was used because the researcher had considered the specification related to the data collection. A total of 160 Pakistani and British research articles were collected. Eighty research articles belonged to Pakistani research, and 80 were British. The researcher conducted an online survey to observe the concerning social science research articles before data collection. After completing an online survey, four journals were selected for the data collection procedure. Those were Pakistani and British journals.

The following four British journals were selected for data collection.

1. Cambridge Journal of Economics
2. The journal of law
3. British journal of humanities and social sciences
4. Journal of language evolution

The following four Pakistani journals were selected for data collection.

1. Pakistan journal of social sciences
2. Technium social sciences journal
3. Pakistan journal of life and social sciences
4. Pakistan journal of commerce and social sciences

3.3 Data Analysis

The descriptive or qualitative data analysis was done in three steps to divide the texts into three clauses. Finding the theme's components was the second step, and mentioning each of the three components was the third. This study covered thematic analysis of research publications authored in Pakistan and the UK. The thematic progression analysis had conducted to check cohesion.

3.4 Procedure of Data Analysis

In the present study, the researcher conducted both qualitative and quantitative analyses to cross-check the data. The qualitative analysis procedure involved the following steps:

- The researcher initially divided the entire text into clauses using a hyphen (-). This approach was applied to 160 research articles authored by Pakistani and British research scholars.
- In the subsequent step, the researcher identified and categorized the components of the theme, namely topical, interpersonal, and textual themes. To facilitate descriptive analysis, different formatting strategies were employed: bold for topical themes, italics for interpersonal themes, and underlining for textual themes. These formatting strategies were utilized to ensure clarity and readability.
- Furthermore, the researcher labeled the components based on the sub-types of the theme, further enhancing the analysis and categorization process.
- Ultimately, the analysis concluded with a comprehensive summary of the findings.

By following this qualitative analysis procedure, the researcher was able to thoroughly examine the data and draw meaningful conclusions from the study.

4. Results

The results were the consequences of thematic analysis of social science research articles written by Pakistani and British research scholars. The thematic analysis was done to realize the meanings by focusing on the theme-rheme components. Theme-rheme functions as a system to organize the text.

(1) Some results of Pak-19 are following:

(1)

(2)

(2) Some results of Pak-20 are following:

(1)

(2)

(3) Some results of Bri-19 are following:

(1)

(2)

(4) Some results of Bri-20 are following:

(1)

(2)

5. Discussion

The results of thematic analysis of social science research articles written by Pakistani and British research scholars belonging to 2019 and 202 have revealed that topical theme is a prominent type among all types of theme overall different sections of data. The interpersonal theme is found less in the analysis, but the textual theme is less than the topical theme and more than the interpersonal theme. This analysis had shown the patterns of cohesion in four different sections of data (Bri-19, Bri-20, Pak-19 and Pak-20), which led the researcher to answer the following questions.

5.1 What is the functional interpretation of the theme found in Pakistani and British research articles?

The study identified three main types of themes: topical theme, UMT theme, and various other types. These thematic elements function as nouns within the text, serving the purpose of conveying information and delivering the intended message to the readers. Nouns, noun complexes, and embedded or dependent clauses were also observed, highlighting the writers' need to employ these devices to effectively communicate their ideas.

Following the UMT theme, the writers showed a preference for using marked topical themes. Marked topical themes, which often consist of prepositional phrases and adverbials, serve as adjuncts or complements. These devices help signal the start of a new paragraph and provide closure to the information presented in previous paragraphs.

The primary objective of the present study was to examine the theme-rheme patterns in social science research articles authored by Pakistani and British research scholars. The study aimed to understand the meaning conveyed through the texts. It employed two types of analysis: a corpus-based analysis to determine the frequencies and percentages of different themes, and a qualitative analysis to explore the data in depth. Through the qualitative analysis, the researcher followed several steps to identify the thematic progression, which revealed the interconnectedness between themes and rhemes within the text. This interconnectedness contributed to the realization of the meanings conveyed in the written texts. The study was driven by a specific purpose, addressing the question at hand.

5.2 How the thematic meaning realized in the written text of Pakistani and British research articles?

The authors of these research articles demonstrated a systematic approach to thematic development, effectively organizing their information in a cohesive manner. Despite the diversity of fields and purposes represented in the research articles, the consistent use of concessive devices and the organization of text through theme and rheme terminologies contribute to the clarity of meaning. Consequently, the application of thematic development procedures and the progression of themes prove valuable in extracting meaning from the texts.

6. Conclusion

The study concluded that the most prominent type of theme in the texts of all different sections is topical, while the textual theme is more prevalent than the interpersonal theme. The topical theme functioned as a noun group in the texts, representing specific entities discussed in each research article. On the other hand, textual themes served as connectors between new and previous information, contributing to the overall coherence of the texts. The analysis of theme types and thematic progression revealed the interconnectedness of information in the texts and demonstrated patterns of cohesion. Notably, the study found that British research articles exhibited more cohesion patterns than Pakistani research articles.

This study offers several practical implications, including:

- English teachers can utilize this study as a valuable tool for assessing the written texts of students and determining the level of cohesion in their writing style.
- Students can benefit from this study by implementing the identified ways of organizing themes to improve their writing style and enhance the coherence of their texts.
- Future researchers can build upon this study by conducting investigations in different subject areas and using diverse sets of data to further explore the topic of theme analysis.

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Bio-note:

Sadia Munir is a research scholar and serving as a visiting lecturer at Government College University, Faisalabad, Punjab, Pakistan. Her areas of interests are systemic functional linguistics, corpus linguistics, and ELT.

Shagufta Afzal is a research scholar and serving as a visiting lecturer at The Islamia university, Bahawalpur, Punjab, Pakistan. Her areas of interests are systemic functional linguistics, corpus linguistics, and ELT.

Hafsa Tazeen is a research scholar and serving as a visiting lecturer at Government College University, Faisalabad, Punjab, Pakistan. Her areas of interests are systemic functional linguistics, corpus linguistics, and ELT.

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